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Imprinting in the placenta is governed by *KDM5D* in the male fetus.

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We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the placenta at first trimester in the male fetus and the female fetus to discover novel sex-specific placental factors. We report here discovery of *KDM5D* as a regulator of sex-specific imprinting in the placenta only in the male fetus. In the placenta of the female fetus, the corresponding imprinting control enzyme(s) appeared to be *KDM6A* and *KDM5C*. Sex-specific imprinting in the human placenta occurs through selective control of *KDM5D*.

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